

Real Wave Quantum Mechanics: Solutions for 2-D Simple Harmonic Oscillator Potential - The Origin of Quantized Energy Levels

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Abstract

Real Wave Quantum Mechanics (RWQM) is applied to a small rectangular grid of Field Rotators (FRs) with a 2-D Simple Harmonic Oscillator (SHO) potential using the matrix eigenvalue method. Quantized 'Eigenstructures' similar to Schrödinger PDFs, but containing additional internal phase structure, are found. However, eigenvalues are complex: application of the matrix to the structures causes a constant change of phase for all FRs. When the frequency of rotation of the FRs is adjusted while leaving the FR spacing unchanged, real eigenvalues of magnitude 1 can be found, indicating the existence of stable self-supporting structures. The adjusted frequencies qualitatively match the energy levels predicted by the Schrödinger equation, having the same spacing and degeneracy structure. It is concluded that RWQM describes a lower level of physical reality which demonstrably (at the qualitative level) leads to Schrödinger's equation and conventional Quantum Mechanics. Electrons are not point particles but are real wave structures distributed through space, as Schrödinger originally contended.

1 Introduction

The paper [Ewins(2021)] introduced the main concepts of Self Interacting Wave Field (SIWF) theory and showed that it gives results consistent with those of Quantum Mechanics (QM) for 1-dimensional systems such as the square well and simple harmonic oscillator (SHO) potentials. Unfortunately, a 1-dimensional system suppresses many of the interesting features of SIWF, which is based on Field Rotators (FRs) and their interaction via physical reaction waves propagating in at least two dimensions. In this paper, small 2-D SHO potential systems are examined using an extended matrix method and the results are confirmed with a method based on convolution.

2 Matrix Method

2.1 Differences between 1-D and 2-D

In 2-dimensions we must consider a grid of FRs each interacting with all the others. Note that choosing a grid formation is not the same as using some arbitrary grid for finite difference purposes, because we are specifying that an FR will exist at each of these points. Of course, nature might have other ideas about the placement of the FRs, but this would require something other than a matrix style of solution. Choosing a matrix for a simple 2-D model might be valid and certainly leads to enlightening results, but for 3-D systems such as the hydrogen atom it is not expected to be viable.

The new feature introduced in the move from 1-D to 2-D is that contributions from FRs not on the same physical rows or columns must be considered. In general these will not be exhibiting Phase Direction Correlation (PDC). For example, in a unit square of FRs, those on opposite corners are separated by $1/\sqrt{2}$ wavelengths: they cannot be in PDC, but their mutual contributions must still be taken into account.

2.2 Building the F_R Matrix

The matrix equation to be solved is

$$F_R \psi^n = \lambda^n \psi^n \quad (1)$$

where each ψ^n is a column vector with one entry for each FR containing a complex number encoding its phase and amplitude. We seek F_R matrices (generated from first principles by RWQM) for which the eigenvectors λ^n are 1, as these correspond to stable eigenstructures¹.

Consider the simplest case of a 2 by 2 array of FR locations

$$\begin{bmatrix} \psi_{0,0} & \psi_{0,1} \\ \psi_{1,0} & \psi_{1,1} \end{bmatrix}$$

The interactions between them can be represented in matrix form as follows:

$$\begin{bmatrix} V_{0,0} & \beta_{\Delta i, \Delta j} & \beta_{\Delta i, \Delta j} & \beta_{\Delta i, \Delta j} \\ \beta_{\Delta i, \Delta j} & V_{0,1} & \beta_{\Delta i, \Delta j} & \beta_{\Delta i, \Delta j} \\ \beta_{\Delta i, \Delta j} & \beta_{\Delta i, \Delta j} & V_{1,0} & \beta_{\Delta i, \Delta j} \\ \beta_{\Delta i, \Delta j} & \beta_{\Delta i, \Delta j} & \beta_{\Delta i, \Delta j} & V_{1,1} \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \psi_{0,0}^n \\ \psi_{0,1}^n \\ \psi_{1,0}^n \\ \psi_{1,1}^n \end{bmatrix} = \lambda^n \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \psi_{0,0}^n \\ \psi_{0,1}^n \\ \psi_{1,0}^n \\ \psi_{1,1}^n \end{bmatrix}$$

For example, the equation for $\psi_{0,0}$ can be read off as

$$V_{0,0} \psi_{0,0}^n + \beta_{\Delta i, \Delta j} \psi_{0,1}^n + \beta_{\Delta i, \Delta j} \psi_{1,0}^n + \beta_{\Delta i, \Delta j} \psi_{1,1}^n = \lambda^n \psi_{0,0}^n$$

¹In this paper the terms 'eigenvector' and 'eigenstructure' are used interchangeably. Eigenvector is the correct term in linear algebra, but eigenstructure is more descriptive of the array of FRs being represented.

Here, n indicates the n 'th eigenvalue/eigenvector pair, and the $\beta_{\Delta_i, \Delta_j}$'s are geometric functions of the relative locations of the two FRs. For example, consider the 1st row 2nd column term. Its function is to compute the contribution to $FR_{0,0}$ from $FR_{0,1}$. The distance between them in this case is 1, and they lie along the same row, allowing the contribution to be calculated as explained in Section 2.3. Now consider the 1st row 4th column entry. In this case the distance between $FR_{1,1}$ and $FR_{0,0}$ is $\sqrt{2}$ and the angle between them (from source to target) is $3\pi/4$. These geometric facts are used in calculating the contribution to be stored in the relevant β at row 1, column 4. The full-size geometric matrix of β s need only be calculated once for each grid. At run time, the off-diagonal entries will be multiplied by the factor α , which recognises that it is the reaction waves which must be summed and these have notional magnitude α times the FR amplitude. The appropriate V s are also inserted along the diagonal at run time.

2.3 Calculating the Contribution

To find the contribution a source FR makes to a target FR, the wave arriving at the target is treated as a spiral wave generated by, and having the characteristics of, the source (i.e. the source phase offset, spin and amplitude multiplied by α). The magnitude and phase of the wave arriving at the target are represented by a complex vector. However, we cannot simply vector-sum all the contributions (as we might in the Feynman' sum over all paths' calculation). We only want to include a wave to the extent to which it contributes to Phase Direction Correlation (PDC). It turns out that, because the geometry is fixed, we can do this once and for all, and incorporate it into the β values.

First, assume that all sources have phase offset zero and amplitude 1. We would like to perform a discrimination calculation on each arriving wave, but what angle should we be discriminating against? In [Ewins(2021)], because we were only studying grids with all the sources having the same zero phase offset, we discriminated against the angle zero. For spin 1 we subtracted the arriving phase of each wave from its direction to give a vector in 'discriminator space' having this angle difference as its angle and the arriving wave amplitude as its magnitude. Vector summation of these contributions over all sources gave the final discriminator vector. We found this had angle $\approx \pi/4$ rather than zero. If we had chosen to discriminate against $\pi/4$ the discriminator vector angle would have turned out to be zero. Thus, when we discriminate against zero, the discriminator gives us the *relative* phase angle of an FR which would have been formed at the target by the waves coming from all the sources (assumed to have zero phase offsets).

How is the fact that the sources can themselves have varying phase offsets handled? The vector ψ^n , eventually to be an eigenvector, will contain a complex number for each FR which encodes its phase offset and amplitude. In the matrix calculation, this value will be multiplied by a β value which is also encoding a discriminator phase and amplitude for a source FR with phase offset zero and unit amplitude ($\times\alpha$). Multiplying two complex numbers we multiply the

magnitudes (thus correctly scaling the amplitude) and add the phases (thus setting the source contribution to the required phase offset).

The matrix F_R turns out to be symmetric but not Hermitian: complex terms either side of the diagonal have the same sign for the imaginary part. (This fact is useful in building the very large matrices involved). The gain terms along the diagonal are all real. Because of its symmetry it proves possible to render the matrix somewhat sparse by cutting off all terms more than some selected distance from the target FR. This still results in a symmetric matrix. This has been used sparingly in the work reported here: most of the results reported are for an 80×80 grid with a cut-off of 80. FRs which have significant magnitudes are usually confined to central zones, which means none of the contributions to them are omitted. FRs in corner regions may lose contributions from source FRs in the opposite corners, but as these are typically at close to zero amplitude anyway, the effect should be minimal ².

2.4 Formulating the Problem

In [Ewins(2021)] the working assumption was made that the reaction wave would be out of phase with the FR from which it originated. The work described below indicates that this was incorrect: QM-like results arise from a reaction wave which is in phase with the FR generating it. This is intuitively justifiable if one thinks of an FR as a mass rotating around a central point from which the non-linear waves forming it are scattered. However, without studying the nature of FRs rigorously, the main justification is that it works. The key components of the matrix are:

- The 'Gains'. These are placed on the diagonal and arise from stochastic boosting, which is calculated by multiplying ψ by a gain function being the sum of:
 - an element which is not dependent on location, V_v , which can be used to tune the model to ensure normalized eigenvalues.
 - the 'potential' (see below)
- The 'Contributions'. These are the combined PDC contributions from all the other FRs, multiplied by the factor α which defines the ratio of the scattered reaction wave amplitude to its source FR amplitude.

What is the relationship between the potential and the gain? It is tempting to think that the area of minimum potential would correspond to maximum gain, perhaps based on the expectation that the structure would roughly focus on such an area. This would require that the potential function - here a paraboloid - be inverted (i.e. a 'mound' of gain rather than a 'pit'). However, this is wrong. The gain function and potential function are the same. This is borne out in the

²It is interesting that some results for full 80×80 matrices show greater distortions from the standard Schrödinger results. It is conjectured that the cut-off reduces some of the unwanted effects arising from using a small full square matrix on a circularly symmetric potential.

results below: eigenstructures are found only for the 'pit' of gain. This raises an interesting question: why does the electron experience a reduction in gain in the vicinity of the proton? The concept of the electrical charge of point particles can no longer be invoked - the electron described by RWQM is not a point!

3 Results

Calculation of the eigenvectors and eigenvalues was carried out in Python, using the Scipy 'eigs' module. Results have been constrained by computing limitations to an 80×80 grid of FRs with a cut-off of 80^3 . To give this some perspective, in the lowest of the hydrogen energy levels the PDF extends radially with significant density out to about 5 times the Bohr radius, which is itself about 20 times the Compton wavelength. For just a 2D calculation this would require an array of up to 300 FRs square. In comparison, the eigenstructures found here fit within a 50×50 FR grid and this only contains half of the FRs it should because all the FRs at the half integer points with phase offset π are omitted (see Section 6.2.1 of [Ewins(2021)]). Their inclusion would double the size of the matrix and exceed the available computer facilities. (The impact of this remains to be checked.) Thus, we are dealing with a 'toy' model, and can only draw qualitative conclusions about its behaviour.

3.1 General Form

Eigenvectors were generated for $\alpha = 1/137$ (whimsical choice) and SHO constant $4e-6$, these values ensuring that ψ magnitudes close to the grid boundaries are vanishingly small. The first 15 eigenvectors are shown in Figure 1. The plots show the magnitudes of the complex vectors rather than their squares, as this preserves more detail. The rows are based on degeneracy levels which are identified and discussed in more detail below. In general terms, plots are an intriguing mixture of those usually presented as Probability Density Functions (PDFs) for this configuration and others not so presented. For comparison with the Schrödinger forms see the results presented by The University of St Andrews found by clicking [here](#). Some are essentially identical to the Schrödinger forms while others look like axially symmetric hybrids⁴.

3.2 Internal Structure

The general form of the eigenvectors is very encouraging, especially considering the highly restricted grid size. They show clear quantization and, with some interesting differences, follow the main predictions of the Schrödinger theory. An important difference is that these eigenvectors exhibit an internal phase

³A 90×90 grid is possible but computing time is impractically long for this essentially qualitative work. A 100×100 grid runs into memory issues on the author's computer.

⁴A recurrent problem with this work is that 'eigs' sometimes returns the structures in a slightly different order following very small adjustments to the parameters.

ψ Magnitude Plots for First 15 Eigenvectors

Figure 1: 80x80 grid with cut-off distance 80, $\alpha = 1/137$, SHO constant $C = 4e-6$

Figure 2: Close up of phase arrows showing alternating phases. Grid intersects are FR locations.

structure not present in the Schrödinger wave solutions. Recall that for a stationary Schrödinger state $\psi^*\psi$ is unchanging with time but the 'phase' of the PDF changes uniformly with time at a rate which equates to the energy of the state. Thus, provided that the electron is at rest, the phase is uniform across the PDF at any instant of time. Now let us look more closely at the Eigenvectors which have been generated in this work. In Figure 2 a close view of the row 2 column 1 eigenvector around one of its peaks is given. The background is a contour map of the magnitude of the vector, whilst the arrows indicate the locations and phases of each FR. As in the case of the 1-Dimensional potential, the first thing to notice is that adjacent FRs are π out of phase with each other. In [Ewins(2021)] it was concluded that it was this feature which enabled stable structures to exist because divergent summation of the harmonic series is replaced with the convergent alternating harmonic series. This is also the reason why scattered contributions 'in phase' lead to a loss at each FR. The four immediate neighbours are approximately out of phase and these are the leading terms in the alternate harmonic series for each cardinal direction.

Figure 3 shows the same eigenvector at a larger scale, which shows more clearly that the phase actually varies *across* the structure. Figure 4 shows the same thing for another eigenvector.

3.3 Eigenvalues

The eigenvalues corresponding to the eigenstructures are complex which implies that the F_R matrix used does not correspond to a stable structure. Instead, the complex nature of the eigenvalues implies a phase inconsistency - FRs are not in phase with the contributions they are receiving from each other. However,

Figure 3: Full scale showing variation of phase direction across the structure

Figure 4: Full scale showing variation of phase direction across the structure

Figure 5: Energy Ratios and V_v s to give Eigenvalue of 1 for each Eigenstructure.

the eigenvalues are a single complex number, so it follows that the phase shift is the same for all FRs. There is an inference here that the F_R matrix has been built using the wrong frequency in the first place. What would happen if F_R was constructed based on a different rate of FR rotation? Simply changing the frequency and the FR spacing would be pointless as it would just be a rescaling of the model. Rather, we must use a frequency which does not match the FR spacing⁵. This has been done in the Python program `PublicMatrixWaveOpt`⁶ which optimizes the wavelength to give a zero phase angle i.e. a real eigenvalue. A similar process is applied to V_v to make the magnitude of this eigenvector 1. The results are shown in Figure 5. Figure 5a shows the energy ratios and Figure 5b the required V_v s. Figures 6a and 6b show the same results averaged by degeneracy groups and illustrate that the energy levels and V_v s are equally spaced as predicted by normal QM.

3.4 Checking the Eigenvalues - Convolution

Once the modified wavelength and V_v have been calculated they can be checked by the process of repeated convolution. Convolution is an important technique in a number of areas, including image and signal processing. It is particularly easy to understand for image processing⁷.

The physical process described by RWQM can be viewed as convolution with a very large kernel, because the result at one FR involves contributions from

⁵A similar effect was found for moving structures of FRs - the spacing of FRs in the direction of motion does not match the wavelength. See [Ewins(2021)]

⁶Available on the Zenodo site. Warning: The program requires repeated applications of 'eigs' and each of these can take a significant time!

⁷Digital images are simply 2-D matrices of numbers (pixels) which indicate the value of a feature such as brightness or redness at each point. Convolution of a digital image is a process by which each pixel in the image is replaced by one which includes some contributions from its neighbouring pixels in a manner prescribed by the 'kernel', which encapsulates the necessary rules. (For example, replace the pixel upon which the kernel is centred by $0.5 \times$ the pixel to its north plus $0.25 \times$ the pixels to its east and west.) The kernel is traversed over the complete image to perform the required process. The process of convolution is so important that much effort has been expended to make its computation highly efficient.

Figure 6: Average Energy Ratios and V_v s by Degeneracy Group

every other FR in a manner which only relies on the geometric relationships between them. These relationships can be built into the kernel once and for all. For the 80×80 array used in this work, the kernel must be 160×160 which is trivial in comparison to the very large arrays required for the matrix method⁸. Checking the results involves building a kernel based on the wavelength and V_v parameters found by PublicMatrixWaveOpt and repeatedly applying it to the corresponding eigenstructure. There are numerical limitations to such a process, but any lack of stability is quickly highlighted. Figure 7 shows 100 iterations applied to a particular FR in eigenstructure 2.

4 Summary and Discussion

The main findings of this work can be summarized as follows:

- The F_R matrix constructed with frequency matching the FR spacing (say ω_0) has ψ_n eigenvectors which, given the size limitations of the toy model, are qualitatively related to¹⁰ the Schrödinger results: i.e. RWQM leads to quantized eigenstructures
- Eigenvalues of the $\omega_0 F_R$ matrix are complex, and have an imaginary part which gives rise to phase drift. This has been interpreted as indicating that the matrix should have been constructed with a lower frequency imposed on the same FR grid spacing.

⁸For compatibility with the cutoff of 80 used in the matrix method, the kernel has zero entries beyond a radius of 80.

⁹The Scipy module `signal.convolve2d` is used in this work as it caters for the large kernel stencil and complex values.

¹⁰If not the same as - it has not been established if the differences merely represent a different basis for the degenerate forms.

Figure 7: Repeated Iterations on Structure 2

- When this is done, kernels having real eigenvectors of magnitude 1 can be constructed with good accuracy. Repeated convolution of each structure with a kernel built using its modified frequency confirms its stability.
- The frequencies (energies) determined for such eigenstructures are qualitatively correlated to those found by the Schrödinger equation. The single state with $n = 1$ has the lowest energy. Thereafter the energies rise with similar spacing and degeneracy structure as the Schrödinger results.

4.1 Re-evaluating the Schrödinger Equation

Schrödinger's equation was a postulate. The logical process leading to its formulation amounted to:

- we need a wave equation, because of de Broglie's findings
- it had better obey energy conservation
- it must explain the energy levels (and thus the absorption/emission spectra) of atoms.

It did these things. In addition, it showed that the energy levels could be associated with structures in physical space describing the 'location' of the electrons. Schrödinger's initial view was that these should be interpreted as mass density distributions. Unfortunately, the Born: 'probability of finding a point particle' interpretation held sway. RWQM gives a strong indication that Schrödinger was right and Born was wrong. Many difficult features of QM disappear in the light of RWQM. (See [Ewins(2021)] for some of these.)

- Spin angular momentum is not 'intrinsic' to a point particle in some unknowable way, but is just normal angular momentum of the FRs distributed across the structure

- The ratio of spin to orbital angular momentum of $1/2$ arises naturally
- the Pauli Exclusion Principle is a demonstrable consequence
- Special Relativity follows directly from RWQM.
- de Broglie's 'matter waves', which form the basis of Schrödinger's wave description of particles in motion, are shown to be one of two mathematical factors of the physical RWQM waves. (The other factor identifies the locations of the FRs)
- As Schrödinger PDFs are only a partial description of an underlying reality, there is no mystery about their 'collapse'. It becomes possible to try to understand particle interactions (measurements) in physical rather than mathematical terms
- Particles (i.e. eigenstructures) *are* extended in space - being in two places at once is no mystery.
- Energy quantization of the form described by the Schrödinger equation simply reflects the requirements for stable RWQM eigenstructures.
- Even though dealing with a toy model, the regular spacing and degeneracy structure for 2-D SHO qualitatively matches the results from conventional QM.

The findings of this paper are qualitative because it is very difficult to process the hugely interactive systems involved. Nevertheless, when coupled with the many other factors described above, the author concludes that Schrödinger's equation is an approximation of Real Wave (SIWF) Quantum Mechanics. It makes calculations far more tractable but it does so at the expense of glossing over an underlying level of reality.

Perhaps it is too soon to quote [Griffiths(1994)] "...it is entirely possible that future generations will look back, from the vantage point of a more sophisticated theory, and wonder how we could have been so gullible." However, RWQM is certainly worthy of further and deeper investigation.

References

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[Griffiths(1994)] David J Griffiths. *Introduction to quantum mechanics*. Prentice Hall, Upper Saddle River, NJ07458, 1994.